

Pedagogical imagination and prospective mathematics teachers' education

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The text presents a reflection on pedagogical imagination (PI) in the context of teacher education. A study group on mathematics education and inclusion was organised with students of a degree course in mathematics. After theoretical studies, the students were invited to imagine mathematics classes in an inclusive perspective. Among the imagined elements, we highlight: the school, students and classes. Based on this experience, we point out important aspects in the PI process including: theoretical study, teacher educator's role, common goals, environment that favours dialogue, and participants' previous experience. The pedagogical imagination in prospective teacher education allowed the prospective teachers to go beyond what is given and to be opened to what could be possible.

Pedagogical imagination in searching for possibilities

The concept of pedagogical imagination is presented in publications by Ole Skovsmose (Skovsmose & Borba, 2004; Skovsmose, 2009, 2011, 2015), which address methodological aspects of research that seeks to transform a situation.

Researching transformations implies that research also investigates possibilities. It is necessary to go beyond what is defined and can be observed, and to confront what is given with what could be different. It is important to search for *what is not, but could be*, which means to investigate alternatives and question what might appear as given.

To Skovsmose the idea of researching possibilities was motivated by an experience with doctoral students in the post-apartheid context in South Africa. The students wanted to follow scientific quality standards, but they also felt uncomfortable by researching the current situation, marked by the consequences left by the apartheid regime. How to research, for example, multicultural mathematics classrooms? It was difficult. The population was still completely segregated, separated into *white, black, coloured* and *Indians* neighbourhoods. Such separation still dominated the South African school context. One approach was to research what did not yet exist in schools, but it could become a reality.

Among the works of the doctoral students, Renuka Vithal's doctoral research (2003) can be highlighted. Vithal investigated whether and how mathematics education could

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contribute to a more democratic South Africa. She explored what would happen in a mathematics classroom, when trying to introduce what she called a social, cultural, political approach to the mathematics curriculum. In the research process, she questioned some criteria and presented the notions of current actual, imagined hypothetical, and arranged situations.

The situation before an educational experiment took place is called current situation (CS). Here one can identify aspects that can be changed. For example, the format of the classes, the method used, the engagement of the students. CS is an important point in the research, but it is also necessary to think about alternatives to this situation.

By imagining possibilities, one arrives at an imagined situation (IS). To get to IS, we reflect on the question: what would happen if something were done differently?

Proposing alternatives to the current situation, based on the imagined situations, leads to an arranged situation (AS). An AS is an alternative to the current situation, different as well from the imagined situation.

Connecting the vertices of the first triangle in Figure 1, we identify the processes involved in researching possibilities. The pedagogical imagination (PI) concerns the relationship between the current and the imagined situations. It is the process that makes it possible to create imagined situations, considering what could happen in a different way.

The relationship between the current and the arranged situation is the practical organization (PO). It is the organisation of actions with departure in the CS based on an IS, but simultaneously acknowledge what is possible giving the practical conditions.

Explorative reasoning (ER) is the process of addressing the imagined situation with departure in the arranged situation. It considers the viability of PI and the innovative elements of the PO. It is a critical interpretation of the two situations.

It is important to emphasise that the transformations through researching possibilities are continuous. This transformation is illustrated in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Researching possibilities (Skovsmose & Borba, 2004, p. 214, 221).

Transformations make integral part of the research process. The changes take place in the current, in the imagination, as well as in the arranged situations. In the following, we will concentrate on the process of pedagogical imagination based in a teacher education case.

Pedagogical imagination: Considerations

The concept of pedagogical imagination as proposed by Skovsmose is inspired by the conception of sociological imagination (Wright Mills, 1959). Sociological imagination is not directed towards given social facts, as being defined through a given social situation. It seeks to identify alternatives to this situation and to open up possibilities for change. This imagination allows us to realise that a given situation is not necessarily something fixed, but can be different.

Considering the educational context, Skovsmose presents the pedagogical imagination as a process that allows exploring possibilities for classroom situations. The imagination can have many different qualities, but it is always confronting the given situation. Both, in relation to research and to actual classroom practices, it is necessary to consider: "(1) what is actual, (2) what could be imagined, and (3) what could be tried out" (Skovsmose, 2011, p. 23). In order to explore educational possibilities, pedagogical imagination is crucial.

School practices involve many contrasts, including those of a socioeconomic nature. Researching possibilities involves imagining alternatives, which might lead to changes. However, it is important to acknowledge that sometimes only small changes are possible, but being small does not mean being irrelevant. Small changes in school education might not result a big social change. Even so, educational changes can make an important difference for many students (Skovsmose, 2011).

Pedagogical imagination does not come out of nothing. Concepts such as democracy, social justice and equity are some resources to take into account (Skovsmose, 2009). Such concepts are fertile ground for a pedagogical imagination. In the case we present here, the fertile ground was a discussion on equity and social justice related to the inclusion of people with disabilities in mathematics classes.

Pedagogical imagination and inclusive education: Reflections from a mathematics teacher education case

In Brazil, the education of people with disabilities is strongly regulated by legislation¹. The increasing dissemination of the right to education has meant that socially underrepresented groups are present at school. As a result of these policies, more and more students with disabilities are attending regular schools. In 2018, there were about 1.2 million enrolments of students aged 4 to 17 years old to whom inclusive education policies are directed², and 92% of them were attending regular school (Censo da Educação Básica de 2018).

The presence of students with disabilities in schools has removed school community from its comfort zone. Among the many uncertainties, insecurities, conflicts and challenges that this community has faced, issues related to pedagogical actions are highlighted (Fernandes & Healy, 2015, our translation). Teachers often feel insecure to deal with the challenge of inclusion and to deal with diversity.

¹ More information of this subject can be found on Penteadó et al. (2018).

² For public policy purposes, the target audience of Special Education is students with disabilities, global developmental disorder and high skills / intellectual giftedness (Decreto nº 7.611, 2011).

For Capellini and Fonseca (2017, p. 120), the difficulties presented in schools “show the need to confront discriminatory practices and create alternatives to overcome them” (our translation).

In this context, inclusive education is configured as an important theme in the education of teachers. It is necessary to think about ways that will lead teachers to consider the diversity present in the school and reflect on the teaching, learning and participation of different students in their classes.

We follow Skovsmose (2019) taking inclusive education as meetings amongst differences. Differences characterise the human beings, and differences live together and interacts with each other. In this sense, the school should be a space where an inclusive culture prevails, which considers and valorises differences of individuals, rather than consider differences as a being problematic. It should provide a curriculum accessible to all students, so that everyone learns (Capellini & Fonseca, 2017).

To address this issue, we organised a doctoral study aiming to understanding possibilities pedagogical imagination opens up for the mathematics teacher education, especially considering Inclusive Education. (The doctoral student is the first author of this paper, the supervisor is the second author.) The data production took place at an institution located in a city of São Paulo State, Brazil. An independent study group was organised with prospective mathematics teachers inspired by Murphy and Lick (1998). Independent groups do not have organisational goals. They are constituted by people with a common interest, seeking to develop personal knowledge. In our case, the common goal was to learn about inclusion of students with disabilities in mathematics classes.

All prospective mathematics teachers from the 2nd, 3rd and 4th years of the course were invited. The research aim and the proposed organisation for the study group were presented. They were also informed that the research had been approved by the University’s Research Ethics Committee and that, among other things, their participation was voluntary and that they could cancel their participation at any time.

The group was constituted by 21 participants. Twelve weekly meetings were held divided into two parts. The Part 1 was dedicated to reading and discussing texts about inclusive education. The Part 2 took departure in the task for the prospective teachers to imagining a school situation including mathematics lessons in classrooms with at least one student with disability. Their imagination should be orientated by an inclusive perspective.

In Part 2, the participants were separated into four smaller groups, called G1, G2, G3, and G4. The teacher educator³ participated in the smaller group meetings, recording the interactions in audio and video, making notes and participating in the discussions, by asking questions and making her own reflections. The proposal involved imagining the school context, the structural conditions, and those involved in the process.

³ In this text, the term teacher educator is used to refer to the researcher, the first author of this article, as this was the role she exercised in the study group. This education action was done in the context of a doctoral research in progress at Unesp, under supervision of the second author.

The departure for the pedagogical imagination was to specify the school, the class, and the students for whom the classes would be planned. All participants brought school experiences, whether as students of basic education, as teachers or from internship experiences or university extension programs. Such experiences were essential when describing school spaces, available resources, rules to be followed, and people with whom they would work to. Many experiences influenced the descriptions.

The school descriptions include the choice of a fictitious school name, the location, the attended public, and whether it was a public or private school. They needed to think about how the physical space was, the institution's teaching concept, the mandatory written tests for assessment of the students. They also needed to imagine the physical organisation of the classroom: the organisation of the desks, maybe in rows, the blackboard quality, and the groups of students in the class. For each of these points, the prospective teachers should justify their choices, for instance by drawing on some memory of lived experience.

The prospective teachers also engaged in characterising the students. They detailed the difficulties, potentials, and characteristics of those with particular difference: someone with a mental or physical disability, with some learning difficulty, with family problems, someone very shy or very talkative. Such characterisations were based on their previous experiences, it could be with an autistic brother, a childhood friend in a wheelchair, a friend from college, etc.

To imagine the classes, the teacher educator suggested a mathematics content to be taught. The choice was made from pre-determined content of the official curriculum. They had to imagine what resources they would use, what activities would be implemented, how the room would be organised, and how the interaction among students would be.

Pedagogical imagination: A discussion on the case

Pedagogical imagination stimulates creativity and offers openness to think about possibilities. All groups recognised a feature of the current situation, as, for example, the presence of the head of the school to evaluate teachers' work in the classroom; the need to maintain discipline in class; the application of assessments according to predetermined standards, and the need to comply with the school curriculum.

However, all groups looked for ways to get beyond these situations. The imagined classes were participatory, investigative, and group-based. The prospective teachers thought of dynamic activities as a way to enhance the participation of all. The students talked to each other, walked around the class, and worked with manipulatives. The organisation of the chairs was no longer in rows, but gave space for students to work in groups. They also explored the idea of students sitting on the floor. Pedagogical imagination opened up possibilities for overcoming barriers with respect to: physical structure, organisation of classrooms, the communication pattern between students and teachers and among students, conventional evaluation mechanisms, among others.

All groups pointed out the need of tests in order to assess learning. Typically, tests are composed of well-defined questions presented in written format and appear as an imposition by school administrations or the government. Sometimes, the prospective teachers recognised that testing can be a form of intimidation and exclusion of students, especially if it is the only format of assessment.

The prospective teachers maintained the test, but included other means for assessing learning, such as engagement in the tasks. Regarding the tests, they thought of ways of favouring all students. For instance, for a blind student or one with motor difficulty, they offered the possibility to do the test orally; for an autistic student with hyper-focus on things from the sea, they elaborated questions that included this topic of interest.

For pedagogical imagination with a collective format as we did, collaboration mediated by dialogue was a crucial aspect. Such collaboration includes negotiations and deliberations. In our case, the imagination was a collective construction from beginning to end: from the presentation of the schools' conditions to the decision about the chosen evaluation methods. This aspect was evidenced by the participant Denise (all names are pseudonyms):

Denise: In the part of thinking about activities, it was a matter of breaking down barriers in the mind, really. There was something I did not think about, but Dani talk, or Kátia, or Isabel. Then I thought: wow! How could I not think of that! And also the importance of sharing things too. When you put several heads together, you know?

The role of the teacher educator in this pedagogical imagination is also an aspect to be highlighted. Samira talks about this.

Samira: I really like this more provocative thing, because it brings us to think. Every time you [teacher educator] provoke us in some way was very important, because it forces us to stop and think: Wait! It brings thoughts that maybe are in our subconscious. But it was important for us stay aware and try to change.

As Skovsmose (2015) considers, pedagogical imagination does not appear out of nothing. In this process, where the teacher educator's intentions, aims, and interventions were decisive. In our case, the goal was for the prospective teachers to think about mathematics classes in an inclusive perspective. With this aim, the teacher educator selected topics and texts discussed in Part 1 and made interventions at the Part 2 meetings of the study group.

An example was when one of the groups was thinking about strategies for working with statistics with a 6th year class of elementary school. In this class, there was a blind student, Josué. Participants were searching for ways to facilitate that everyone would be able to read the information contained in a three-dimensional graph. The graph was constructed by the students to represent the result of an investigation they carried out on their shoes number. The interaction among participants in the study group can be illustrated by the following transcript:

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- Denise: We have to think about the blind student.
- Kátia: Maybe we could make the axes with glitter paper, because it is very rough. We could also, on the axis that has the shoe numbers, cut out the digit in EVA⁴ with glitter and he could run his hand on it.
- Danilo: Yes, we could think of using an EVA with glitter and one without glitter to differentiate.
- Kátia: And so, we do the same for all groups, because it is more beautiful. Furthermore, we do not differentiate only one. More attractive. More colourful.
- Denise: The good thing about EVA is because it is a cheap material. If it is not available at the school, one can buy it.
- Teacher educator: Yes. But one thing I kept thinking ... You talked about cutting out the digits in EVA for the blind to read ...
- Denise: Wow, guys! But is this how he reads?
- Isabel: I do not know.
- Kátia: I think so. I have seen selling ready-made EVA digits. I bought some other day, it is cheap.
- Denise: But Kátia, it is not Braille.
- Danilo: That is what I thought now. It is not Braille.
- Kátia: That is right. This student reads in Braille.
- Denise: Yes ... He feels the cut digit, but he does not read it.
- Isabel: Absolutely!
- Danilo: Wow! How could we not have thought of that?

The imagined strategy to make possible for Josué to read the information on the graphics was not really helpful. The group looked for a way for him to get access to information through hand touch. They tried to include him. However, how did Josué read? To reach this observation, an intervention of the teacher educator was necessary, inviting them to reflect.

The group realised that they would not know how to write the information in Braille. At this moment, the teacher educator introduced the reglete: an instrument similar to a ruler, used to write in Braille on a piece of paper using a kind of pen for puncture. It provided a new resource for the prospective teachers. As Denise concluded: “Then we will have a reglete.” So, the reglete was used in this class.

The process of pedagogical imagination was based on negotiation through dialogue: one says something, other complements, reflects, argues. It was a dynamic process.

Table 1 highlights important aspects of the process of pedagogical imagination in the education of mathematics teachers, based on our case. These aspects were pointed out in the analysis of the interactions among the study group participants and the pedagogical imagination process they performed.

⁴ Ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) is a synthetic foam that is widely used for crafts and schoolwork.

Aspect	Detailing
Theoretical Study	The role of theoretical study on inclusive education was shown during the conversations and actions of prospective teachers. E.g., when they were concerned about doing activities where everyone could read the graphs, even if all the graphs needed to be also in Braille. It shows the search for universal design for learning, a concept that was discussed in Part 1 of the study group.
Teacher educator role	Teacher educator is the person who guides the imagination process, selects texts of theoretical support, and intervenes in the discussions. The importance of her interventions was highlighted in Samira's speech. It was also in the transcribed dialogue, when the teacher educator led the participants to question how to provide Josué condition to read the graph.
Common theme/ goal	The fact that the participants had a common goal – mathematics classes from the inclusion perspective – was essential for the collaboration. Participants were always looking for strategies that would allow everyone to participate and learn.
Environment that favours dialogue	Due to its collective nature, dialogue was the way by which pedagogical imagination took place. Dialogic communication permeated interactions, negotiations, and deliberations for decisions. As Denise told, sometimes a person does not think about something, but some colleague comments invite for making new reflections. One learns together with others.
Consider participants' experiences	The whole process involved specificities and expectations for each context, which in addition to the theory studied, are influenced by the experiences of each one who participated. As we pointed out, all the imagined schools, students, and classes had characteristics of the participants' previous experiences.

Table 1: Aspects of the pedagogical imagination process in prospective teacher education

Final remarks

In this text we discuss the possibilities of pedagogical imagination in mathematics teacher education. Pedagogical imagination is the process that leads from a current situation to an imagined one. Our current situation was the fact that mathematics teachers find it difficult to cope with inclusive mathematics classes, particularly when it comes to classes with students with disabilities. In this process of pedagogical imagination, everything was imagined: schools, classes, and students. Everything was characterised in details, based on each participant's experiences.

From a current situation, possibilities to change it can be imagined, and this leads to an arranged situation. After a pedagogical imagination process, a current situation will never be the same. Imagination changes this reality.

Pedagogical imagination is free. It goes as far as the imagination allows. That is why the inputs are important: the theoretical support, the role of the teacher educator, and the interaction among the participants. Our case points to the importance of the collective aspect, of dialogue. It shows the richness of imagining with the others.

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